

ADDRESSING CULTURAL DIVERSITY THROUGH RESPONSIVE TEACHING AT THE HIGHER SECONDARY LEVEL

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18480532>

Abstract: This paper aims to study the perceptions of teachers regarding Cultural Mosaic and Culturally Responsive Teaching. Culturally responsive teaching is an umbrella term which consists of a variety of methodologies. In all approaches of culturally responsive teaching, an equity-centered approach stresses learners' ethnicity at the core of the learning process and uses the "cultural knowledge, previous experiences, frames of reference, and learning styles of culturally diverse scholars". In an environment where a cultural Mosaic situation prevails, culturally responsive teaching shall be promulgated as it reduces the stress level of learners which results in a better teaching-learning process. According to different studies, students come with a lot of potential and a good teacher must explore those potential. Such type of attitudes and conditions accommodating diverse cultural students pave the way for Culturally Responsive teaching. A case study design was adopted due to the nature and characteristics of the concerned study. A systematic sampling technique was used. The researcher held Interviews of 36 teachers on 10 open-ended structured questions in the session 2021-22. Thematic Analysis was used for the collected data. As a teacher, we may build on those potentials that are already brought by students in the classroom. Parents may also be involved in that regard as their role can't be ignored in the teaching-learning Process. Teachers may be encouraged by the head of the institution to learn about students' cultures that have representation in the classroom. Provisions of internet in Libraries, Computer Labs through Multi-Media or may be provided by the administration in a type of downloaded videos for watching at home. All such type of activities and provisions of facilities may be provided to the staff and students for their grooming to tackle the Cultural Mosaic classrooms' students in a way that promote and enhance the performance of students.

Keywords: Cultural Mosaic, Culturally Responsive Teaching, Equity, Frame of References, Learning Styles, Stress Level, Parents involvement.

Introduction

Pakistan is a state where different types of people with unique cultural values live in known cultural groups like Punjabi, Pashtuns, Baluchi, Sindhi etc.

It has different types of geographical locations due to which characteristics, culture varies a lot e.g., mountainous ranges like Muree in Punjab and KP, different districts with diverse demographics of

Khyber Pakhtunkhwa; Cold areas like Chitral, Northern Areas of Pakistan, Gilgit Baltistan, Islands in the area of Sindh situated in Bhira Arab, Areas of rich cultivatable land in Punjab and Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, desert areas like Thar, Cholistan and Baluchistan. With the change in geographical location way of living is also being changed. This diversity can also be observed in values, languages, traditions, professions, skills etc. (Mazur et al., 2010; Farooq, 2013). Such type of diversity makes Pakistan a lively country due to the existence of the Cultural Mosaic Phenomenon.

Although at one angle cultural diversity is the blessing of Allah and on another angle, it increases challenges. It is our responsibility as a nation to benefit from diversity's positive aspects rather than biases, inequality and its other negative aspects. Pakistani Society will have to show its strong commitment to educating and training its students in cultural mosaic reality. For this purpose, those who are related to the teaching-learning process will play their sensible part in upbringing their students to play their role in the global world community as leaders. Pakistan believes in Cultural Mosaic rather than Melting Pot, that's why Muslims, Christians, Hindus, and other minorities live in harmony with the majority group of Muslims by keeping their ethnic identities (Khan, Shehnaz, & Ahmed, 2000; Oda, 2007). In Cultural Mosaic classrooms, the existence of diverse opinions is a fact and such diversities must be harmonized in a peaceful manner (Jehn, Northcraft, & Neale, 1999; Pelled, Eisenhardt, & Xin, 1999; Webber & Donahue, 2001).

In 20th and 21st Century teachers are equipped with modern pedagogies and approaches, which may be resulted in better performance of students. The situation is not the same as it is being expected from the teachers and from the institutions for which a program of No Child Left Behind in USA was started. In Pakistan Taleem e Balighan, Nai Roshni Schools, Mohalla and Maktab Schools were started to enhance the literacy of the country. By different studies it was concluded that gap is existed in the performance of students and teachers both. This gap of performance is quite concern able for the education ministries not only in Pakistan but for the developed countries too like USA. Performance of a teacher depends on scholastic performance of the students. Teachers try and adopt different types of approaches to enhance performance of learners. Although they try their best but positive results are not found in the achievement tests of students. One of the reasons for this gap of students' and teachers' performance was found in cultural diversity and ignoring the cultural background and prior experiences of learners especially of the ethnically minority students at higher secondary level. Number of ethnically minority students are on increase in Pakistan too. What types of approaches and teaching methodologies may be adopted to overcome the gap of performance of learner and teachers of diverse cultures? Teachers are unaware of such type of approaches which may minimize the performance gap of students and teachers and it also emerges in failure to nourish ideologies, inability to create consensus on decisions and incompetency to achieve a common goal . So cultural diversity of

students is a challenge for a teacher that need to be addressed (Giroux, 1981; Singal, 2008).

Literature Review

According to Tomlinson 2001, over time, heterogeneity in educational institutions is increased considerably. The number of students of 2nd mainstream languages like Pashtu, Panjabi, Saraiki, Sindhi and other languages increased rapidly along with the first mainstream language of Urdu which is not a mother tongue of any province in Pakistan. In a classroom teacher faces such type of challenges i.e., The diversity of 2nd language learners is as greater as their degree of experience, as well as native tongues and the support that they get from their homes towards schools in their nourishment concerns, which also vary in nature (Cohen & Lotan, 2014). In schools, students are observed with attention deficit and related disorders. Observance of learning disabilities disturbs learners fundamentally in all classrooms. So is the case of students coming to classrooms with highly innovative skills and understandings? These students are not only different in physical abilities but they have differences culture-wise too. A lot of students came to school with several Home-Based problems that are a heavy burden on the tender shoulders of students (Delpit, 2006). Such types of realities can be observed with numerous students. In rare cases an able student can only be succeed to achieve his goal who belongs to 2 nd mainstream language family and who is economically lagging in society. In such a scenario as teachers, we will come across the fact that learners learn in different ways rather than a single methodology. Some students

will learn just by listening, some by performing an act, some will learn individually, some in groups of students; some will learn with speed, while some will learn by reflecting on themselves (Gardner, 1993). As a teacher, we know that learners inspired by diverse subjects or diverse fields and inquisitive minds and motivation are powerful instruments for learning. If someone wants to teach effectively, will have to care about all the above-mentioned facts. To make it possible to arrange such type of teaching-Learning environment where different types of students learn effectively, it needs that teachers not only play their role to enhance their competencies to understand cultural mosaic realities as well as differentiated instructions to be adopted along with curricular activities may also be arranged in such a way that all individuals who may belong to any culture or they may have any type of capabilities may benefit from the teaching of a teacher and learn from different type of curricular activities those are prevailing in the institutions to gain their goal of life (Shade, 1989; Means et al., 1991).

Culturally Responsive Teaching

In an environment where a cultural Mosaic situation prevails, culturally responsive teaching may be promulgated as it reduces the stress level of learners that emerges in a better teaching-learning process (Eilam, 1997; Triandis, 2000; Ely & Thomas, 2001). The 21 st Century considered and gave value to the diversity of cultures due to developments in Information and Communication Technologies (ICT), Scientific ventures. ICT and Scientific advancement resulted in close relationships of masses to a great extent Globally (Freeman,

Freeman, & Ram'irez, 2008). Cultural Mosaic brought changes in the classroom environment too. Cultural Mosaic existed in a single classroom in the present century. All-inclusive ideology and peaceful relations among all diverse strata of the masses of a country are needed in cultural mosaic realities as they existed the world over. It is not restricted to the people of a country but the education system of a country should also take care of cultural mosaic by the creation of culturally responsive teaching (CRT). CRT or culturally responsive pedagogy tries to create a cultural mosaic environment and ensure respect for the diversity between ideologies and ethnicities (Khatoon, Rehman, & Ajmal, 2011).

Awareness of Cultural Diversity

Cultural Mosaic ideology has a positive impact if teaching staff and institutions were aware of cultural diversity as well as gave value to it, along with the chairperson of educational institutions. It is a joint venture rather than a single effort of teaching staff, parents and heads of Educational institutions for the betterment of a student to achieve his goal. As the researcher discussed above in detail the two social ideologies of cultural mosaic and Melting Pot are used as a metaphor too in the context of Canadian and USA ideologies. Both differ slightly in meaning. Cultural Mosaic is such type of ideology that depict diversity in which its members keep their original cultures abreast and in Melting Pot masses lose their original cultural identities and merge themselves into the mainstream culture of a country (Hofstede, 1991; Triandis, 2000). Believers in cultural Mosaic (Canadians) and Melting Pot (People of USA) have a pride in their ideologies for a long. In natural

Phenomenon, White Sun Light is a combination of Cultural Mosaic and Melting Pot. In form of White Light, it shows Melting Pot. Diverse Colours are assimilated in a Whit Light but when it goes through the drops of rain in the shape of a Rainbow it emerges in a Cultural Mosaic. It spreads the beauty of its diverse colours on one side and gave a brilliant picture of the Rainbow as a whole on another side. In short, nature also supports cultural Mosaic reality. Some Educationists narrated this reality as a Salad Bowl theory which says that "those people who migrated from other regions, and countries live their life with the same rituals and customs as they were practicing in their native countries" (Khatoon et al., 2011).

From the above review of related literature, it becomes evident that in urban areas of Islamabad, homogeneous classrooms are no more existed, that's why teachers have to adapt their teaching according to the changed situation, which has challenges for teachers. Heads of Educational Institutions may also have an awareness of the cultural mosaic of their staff as well as of the students. The environment of educational institutions may promote cultural mosaic and there should be activities that help bring out the capabilities and indigenous expertise of students for the contribution of students' knowledge towards the achievement of a common goal of the institution. Pre-Service and In-Service teachers' training is a necessary tool to equip the teachers to enhance their competencies to cope with the culturally mosaic classrooms to achieve good results scholastically. Where performance of the students might show positive trends, it depicts, that teaching techniques

those adopted by the teachers are adequate and according to the individual differences of students and are according to their psychological needs.

The objective of this study was to find out the perspective of teachers regarding cultural mosaic and culturally responsive teaching at the higher secondary level. To know about the challenges faced by the teachers in culturally diverse classrooms in the context of Cultural Mosaic. To explore the perceptions of Teachers regarding Culturally Responsive Teaching as a viable strategy at the Higher Secondary level. To find out whether Heads of Higher secondary level were aware of the phenomenon of Cultural Mosaic and to know what is their contribution towards the creation of a Psychological work environment for the achievement of educational targets. To investigate whether Cultural Diversity Day is celebrated every year along with other international days.

Research Methodology

The following methodology was adopted for the study:

Research Design

The case study design was adopted due to the nature and characteristics of the concerned study. Point of view of teachers regarding cultural diversity, CRT, Challenges of CRT, Viability of CRT etc needs a prolonged observation of students by the teachers. Therefore it needs the approach of case study. It allows thorough, multi-faceted investigation of complex issues in their real-life context. Observation of students in their school setting paved the way for Case study design which is well recognized in the field of social science especially

and in other fields ordinarily. It is a naturalistic design and the purpose is to learn as much as possible about an individual or group so that the information can be generalized to many other groups. The case study design allows a great deal of information which can be collected on unusual case (Yin, 1994; Stake, 1995). According to Stake, 1995 the case study design is particularly suitable for the understudy phenomenon i.e. The Cultural Mosaic and Culturally Responsive Teaching especially in Pakistan is a unique and studies are conducted in the recent three decades only.

Types of the Case Study Design

Types of case studies are: Collective Case Studies in which the researcher might study a group of people in a certain setting or look at an entire community; Descriptive Case Studies in which the researcher might start with a theory, then the subjects are observed, and the information gathered is compared to the pre-existing theory; Explanatory Case Studies in which causal investigations are conducted; Exploratory Case Studies is used as a preamble to further, more in-depth research; Instrumental Case Studies are conducted when individual or a group allows researchers to understand more than what is initially obvious to observer; and The Intrinsic Case Studies is used when the investigator has a personal interest in the case e.g Jean Piaget observation of his own children are an example of Intrinsic case studies that developed to a psychological theory. Most commonly used types of the case study design are intrinsic, instrumental and collective case study.

The researcher used the collective case study design as a group of teachers who already observed their students with the intent to find out the perspective of teachers regarding cultural mosaic and culturally responsive teaching at the higher secondary level. To know about the challenges faced by the teachers in culturally diverse classrooms in the context of Cultural Mosaic. To explore the perceptions of Teachers regarding Culturally Responsive Teaching as a viable strategy at the Higher Secondary level. To find out whether Heads of Higher secondary level were aware of the phenomenon of Cultural Mosaic and to know what is their contribution

Table 1

Population of the Study

1	Higher Secondary Level Institutions	29
2	Teachers who were teaching at Higher Secondary Level	116
3	Students of Class XI & XII	3480

Sample

A systematic sampling technique was used. The number of Higher Secondary Schools and Colleges that were selected as the population were 29. The sample of the study was 36 teachers from 9 Higher Secondary level institutions which are located in the Urban Areas of Islamabad. These Class In-Charges were selected for interview as they observe their students more closely than the Subject Teachers at Class XI & XII and are ready to participate in the study and were the focus of this investigation. A care was also taken in the selection of sample

Table 2

Sample of the Study

towards the creation of a Psychological work environment for the achievement of educational targets. To investigate whether Cultural Diversity Day is celebrated every year along with other international days.

Population

Population of the study was all teachers and especially Class In-charges who were teaching at Urban 1 and Urban 2 among the 432 educational institutions of Islamabad, those were working under the management of Federal Directorate of Education, Ministry of Federal Education & Professional Training at the Higher Secondary level.

teachers who taught their students for a year or more than a year, as they have an ample observation to make an opinion about their students. Permission for interviewing the teachers was sought out from the Federal Directorate of Education. They have not only granted permission but instructed the Principals of the sample institutions to help the researcher in the collection of Data. The researcher held Interviews of 36 teachers on 10 open-ended structured questions and one was an optional question on which teachers were interviewed in the session 2021-22.

1	Institutions visited	9
2	Interviewed Teachers who were teaching at H.S.L & were Classroom In Charge for a year or so	36
3	Students of Class XI & XII	1668

Research Protocol or Ethical Consideration

For ethical consideration two strategies were adopted by the investigator. Permission from the concerned university was sought out and permission from Federal Directorate of Education Islamabad was also sought out with the intent of cordial investigating from the teachers, and data from sample selected might be collected in an efficient manner. Not only permission of Parent Department was sought out but a request was made to the concerned Principals too. Anonymity insurance from the researcher's side was also given to the teachers, that the collected data will be used only for the research purpose. Questionnaire was briefed to the teachers in urdu too. Queries were also explained on the spot to the participants.

Data Analysis

In this study thematic Analysis was used for the collected data. According to Aronson (1995); Attride-Stirling (2001) thematic analysis is a widely used qualitative research technique. Benefit of thematic analysis is its flexibility and it is a method that can be used for analyzing text data. It is a systematic method of classifying, forming, and offering understanding into, patterns of meaning (themes) across a dataset. The flexibility has made this approach useful for a variety of researchers. Themes emerged from the collected data that are discussed in detail. The study was conducted to

analyze Cultural Mosaic classrooms and culturally responsive teaching from the perspective of those teachers who were practically involved in the pedagogy of sample classrooms' students in urban areas of Islamabad. These teachers know their students well and have a better idea about their teaching learning Process. Due to accessibility and flexibility thematic research analysis tool was used for the data analysis. Thematic analysis offers a way into qualitative research that teaches the mechanics of coding and analyzing qualitative data systematically, which can then be linked to broader theoretical or conceptual issues. Thematic analysis suits multimethods research being conducted by research teams, where not everyone is a qualitative expert. In thematic analysis combination of coding and analysis are used. It has six phases (Braun & Clarke, 2006) i.e. Familiarizing yourself with the data e.g., transcripts of interviews, responses to qualitative surveys; Generating initial codes; Searching for themes; Reviewing potential themes; Defining and naming themes; Producing the report. In this study data was collected in the form of responses through the tool of interview from the practicing teachers who observed their students for more than a year or more. Thematic analysis was the most suitable for such type of collected data. So the researcher filtered the data from these six phases for responses gathered from the point of view of

practicing teachers who are working in Federal Directorate of Educational institutions and at last conclusion was reached after thoughtful deliberation on the coded data.

Mosaic

Mosaic is a proverb that is used to show the cultural diversity of a group in an organization, in a society, in an institution etc. in such a way that each group sustain their cultural identities in an original capacity. Such a group may not melt or amalgamate their cultural identities in the dominant group. If a group merge their cultural identities with a dominant group of a nation or society such a type of merger will be called a Melting Pot. In simple words, Cultural Mosaic or salad bowl metaphors depicts Ethnic Heterogeneity and Melting Pot shows groups' Ethnic Homogeneity (Kluckhohn & Murray, 1953; Hofstede, 1991; Triandis, 2000).

Cultural Mosaic vs Melting Pot

Cultural mosaic refers to multiculturalism but people from different cultures live together maintaining a multicultural society where people of different culture form and exhibit a similar pattern of living together, eating and other interactions. They did not show a convergence of cultures. Melting pot refers to the multicultural society where people of different cultures form and exhibit a similar pattern of living together, eating and other ways of interaction, they show convergence of cultures. Cultural Mosaic people of different cultures interact but maintain the characteristics of their own culture. In the melting pot, people of different cultures assimilate other cultural characteristics and acquire a new culture.

Mosaic Classrooms

Different cultural backgrounds are quite visible in the students of a classroom at the higher secondary level. Over time these cultures of students mingled with their own identities in a manner that they exercise and exhibit their cultural values and rituals in the classroom. In this way, the classroom is a cultural mosaic instead of a melting pot. The metaphor CM refers to a student's cultural background. They belong to different cultures of Pakistan. CM and MP both indicate the diversity of students, which can be observed in students as they are from different parts of Pakistan. Both terms depict diversity, which exists in students of educational institutions. Cultural mosaic indicates the diversity of culture among students which depicts mosaic rather than a melting pot as they are glad in presenting their cultural items instead of others. Teachers in such types of classrooms should be interested in fostering cultural awareness in the classroom. Teachers may actively demonstrate care about students' cultural, emotional and intercultural needs.

The extent of cultural diversity in classrooms

Teachers responded and shared this information with the researcher, that students from different provinces show their cultural trends in the form of language, eating and living style. Our institute has numerous diverse cultures and ethnic groups such as the Punjabis, Kashmiris, Sindhi and tribal culture of Baloch. Several languages are spoken in Pakistan. Students from different regions have different dress and diets. Teachers should encourage students to beware of different socio-economic statuses.

Students from different parts of Pakistan came here to get knowledge at capital institutions.

According to some other teachers cultural diversity is not so prominent in classroom students. Different cultures and backgrounds do seem exhibit in their classroom so much. During the academic session, on national days like the 14th of August, and the 23rd of

March, local festivals are arranged which depict cultural diversity. Students from KP, Punjab, GB & AJK are here in my classroom, which depicts

Figure 1

Challenges of Cultural Mosaic & CRT	Mutual Respect
	Awareness of Cultural Norms
	History & Characteristics of Cultures
	Cultural Honour
	Celebrations of Cultural Activities
	Addressal of Heterogeneity
	CRT Techniques
	Language and Norms Barriers
	Prior Knowledge and experiences
	Learning of Indigenous Languages
	Shortage of Resources for CRT.
	Shortage of Trained staff
	Parents & Public Involvement
Awareness of Principles' regarding CRTs	

Figure No. 1 shows different types of challenges that are faced by a teacher in cultural mosaic classrooms. These are:

1. **Mutual Respect:** To have respect for the culture of others is necessary for cultural Mosaic Classrooms. In absence of mutual respect culturally responsive teaching might not be effective. Mutual respect is a gigantic task to achieve and pave way for intolerance among students which becomes a challenge for a teacher.

different cultures, so diversity exists. Yes, cultural diversity exists in students of my class. Another teacher adds that cultural diversity exists in my classroom as students from other parts of the country instead of Islamabad are present in my classroom.

The challenges of culturally responsive teaching

Challenges related to Cultural Mosaic Culturally Responsive Teaching that is pointed out by the teachers were:

2. **Awareness of Cultural Norms:** Effective teaching needs an awareness of cultural Norms (Stichter et al., 2009), Cultural mosaics promote cultural norms and eye contact (Loreman, 2007). Cultural Mosaic classrooms have more than a single culture, due to which cultural norms' awareness becomes a challenge for a culturally responsive teacher **History & Characteristics of Cultures:** According to (Meister & Melnick, 2003) to know norms of diverse cultures, a culturally responsive

teacher may know the history and characteristics of cultures his/her students have in the classroom.

3. Cultural Honour: Don't misinterpret the behaviours of students in a cultural mosaic environment. These behaviours need consideration of cultural honour (Loreman, 2007).

4. Cultural Celebrations: Villegas, 2002 pointed out that cultural celebration are results in a conducive atmosphere that create a non-threatening environment. To fill the gap in cultural mosaic classrooms and to keep the expectation high regarding the capabilities of learners, the physical environment of the educational institution may be arranged with ethnically relevant pictures, posters, teaching materials and bulletin boards and cultural celebrations.

5. Address Diversity: Successes depend on the teacher and it might be achieved through a culturally well-informed teacher who knows how to use their cultural information, experiences related to a past life, learners' frames of reference, and presentation styles of ethnically heterogeneous learners to form learning in a more significant and in a more successful way which may benefit them in future.

6. CRT Techniques: To overcome the challenges of cultural mosaic and culturally responsive teaching, the teacher may critically reflect, participate in Book Club, firsthand learning experiences, community walks etc. are the techniques to lessen the challenges of cultural mosaic (Baldwin, Buchanan, & Rudisill, 2007).

7. Language and Norms Barriers: Lack of communication creates low confidence resulting in social isolation among ethnically heterogeneous

learners in a class (Jordan, Schwartz, & McGhie-Richmond, 2009).

8. Prior Knowledge and experiences: Teachers are unaware of the fact that the connections they opt for to help learners in understanding concepts being taught are in fact "ethnic," reflective of the lived, familiar experiences of students who are not students of color, leaving students of color in a state Foreword of disconnect, and often a deep sense of frustration. Past experiences and cultural context have the relevance that would enable them to be engaged and make meaning, but they are unable, so their innate ability for high levels of cognitive processing is hindered (Hammond, 2014).

9. Learning of local languages: For CRT teachers to teach effectively in ethnically heterogeneous classrooms, he has culturally competent to convey theories, and concepts at the time of need. Therefore local languages may be learnt by the teachers to facilitate the students.

10. Shortage of resources for culturally responsive teaching: Gonzales et al, 2015, different types of tools are required for CRT teaching i.e. Multimedia, Internet, Smartboards, USBs, etc. Such type of resources lacking in Public schools

11. Shortage of teaching staff: During the interview, a lot of reservations are showed about the shortage of teachers due to which teachers are reluctant to experiment with new models.

12. Parents and Public Involvement: Parents and Public Involvement in CRT create possibilities for the best learning environment (Ogbu, 1992).

13. Cultural Mosaic Beliefs create a conducive environment for learning, but a considerable lacking on part of Principals is found.

In other words one can conclude that a classroom having multiculturalism creates an environment of huge challenges for the teacher, students tend to their culture and have some sort of prejudices against other cultures and languages. They try to consider themselves superior to others. In extreme cases harassment cases increase to a greater level. It is a new terminology for us. In the past decade educational environment has changed over time and has become more complex. Incomparable sharing with students and parents. Students are reluctant to engage in the classroom at first and they have a language barrier. Along with the above-mentioned challenges funds available for cultural practices are scarce. Though there are some hurdles in teaching to different cultural students. But where there is a will there is a way. Students get used to each other outcomes and likewise, the teacher can handle the students by keeping in mind the different cultures of students, Languages, and uniform attitudes towards all students. No one is restricted to present his point of view in my classroom. Opportunities were given to express themselves. We make interaction with students' parents on regular basis. Some other mentioned challenges are hereunder:

Strategies to address the heterogeneity of students

Students shall be given awareness of respecting all other cultures, allowing them to interact with one another, and share their views. Explain the history and characteristics of other cultures. Sharing

information and gifts is a way of creating honor for other cultures. Different activities are promulgated in which all students participate in these activities and in this way they learn other cultures and languages. Different teaching techniques are in use to address diversity. I should provide a conducive environment for the students. The teacher should aware of students' cultural, and language-related problems. Teachers have to learn more about linguistics. Awareness about language errors shall be also given to students for a better understanding of cultures and persons. Cultural awareness shall be spread through audio and videos. I will use a different types of teaching methodologies to suit diversity. By giving them examples from their culture. Relate examples from that culture. Formation of different projects and items through students having some cultural background can be helpful to get indigenous expertise. Group learning, A caring attitude, use of students' points of view in the projects are such types of strategies that can address diversity. Heterogeneity is addressed with the help of a friendly atmosphere in the classroom. Dealing with students with respect, and equal opportunities to express themselves are the strategies which were used to address the diversity".

Prior knowledge, experience and expertise

According to the findings those were inferred from the data collected after thematic analysis some steps are necessary and helpful for an environment of Culturally Responsive Teaching. These are; Create an environment of discussion and debate in which teacher's role is to facilitate the students. Make them busy with various projects so that they may share

their previous knowledge and connect it with new knowledge for better understanding and comprehension. When they are busy with other activities they use their previous knowledge in a new situation and construct new knowledge through discussion and inquiry-based learning. Friendliness is used to explore the realm of students' experiences. I need to know more about students' shortcomings during collaboration in projects and try to overcome the pressure of students due to socio-economic issues. Prior knowledge is acquired by arranging discussions in class and giving them

topics about something. Brainstorming may help us to explore their knowledge and understanding and experiences of students through Project teaching, cultural companions and presentation. Students were given opportunities to share their experiences in the projects they were asked to complete. Giving them tasks during projects is a way to explore the student's prior knowledge. Native language is used to the minimum, although no one can deny its impact to achieve ample participation in educational activities by the students.

Figure 2

The Viability of Culturally Responsive Teaching

Figure No. 2 shows how culturally responsive teaching might be made possible. CRT viability depends on:

1. Family Participation,
2. making classrooms a type of mini-society,
3. In-Service and Pre -Service training in CRT is necessary,
4. A period of 35 or 40 minutes is not enough for culturally responsive teaching which also made it a challenge for a teacher but proper training and practice made this approach possible.

5. Language proficiency is also a prerequisite for teachers to teach in cultural mosaic classrooms. Pre-Service and In-Service professional training for teachers is necessary to know about the teaching techniques to address the challenges of cultural mosaic classrooms, have ample knowledge of different cultures, peculiar notions of cultures, different learning styles of students, how to get the students' potentials in the classroom, to keep high expectations from students rather than consider them deficit in capacities, learning of different

dialects of languages those have representations in the classroom, all such type of knowledge can get through thorough professional training before induction and then continuous professional development is necessary after induction of the teachers. In such a way one can say that culturally responsive teaching will have its roots in educational institutions otherwise teachers have to face challenges in the above-mentioned facts. Some other points were pointed out were:

Contribution of Principals in the creation of a culturally conducive atmosphere

The principal creates a cooperative environment for students to hear and share students' problems and conducts PTM at the end of every term. The Principal encourages the creation of a lucrative and conducive environment of learning for all students by conducting periodic PTM and taking initiatives in the light of feedback provided by parents belonging to different regions or cultures. Parent interaction exposes a variety of diverse experiences that motivate the students to cooperate and solve daily life situations/problems. She can encourage teachers, and staff families by providing opportunities for conducting PTM, so that parents from different cultures interact with students providing different cultural information. Our principal is very cooperative in this regard. Teachers are facing problems, especially in rural and remote areas. They are sharing their resources for the welfare of learners. Teachers have a lack of training and insufficient resources. The role of the head is

Figure 3

Steps Necessary for the Heads of Educational Institutions

very important as a facilitator. Our head is a very supportive person. The Head's contribution is necessary for developing a conducive environment for such culturally diverse classes. By involving teachers, parents and students. The contribution of the head is very important to create a conducive atmosphere and promulgating such strategies. Having a role model attitude and support initiative, that synergies the whole staff. The head is always there to support a positive step. He has a supportive attitude. The Principal of the educational institution according to interviewees may have:

1. Knowledge of the extent and what type of cultural diversity exists in his/her institution regarding staff and students i.e., Cultural Mosaic or Melting pot and then decide what he can do in that respect to facilitate his staff and students to achieve their set tasks smoothly, efficiently and with the increase in performance.
2. The Principal of the institution may ensure that all his staff accept cultural diversity to avoid biases which hinder organizational goals.
3. The Principal of an educational institution may make sure that existing diversity plays a positive role rather than a negative one.
4. All cultural activities shall be celebrated with all staff and students, so that a conducive environment may be created for all learners.
5. By all the mentioned above steps Heads of institutions can make culturally responsive teaching viable otherwise it will be failed.

<p>1. Knowledge of Extent and sort of Heterogeneity in an educational staff.</p>	<p>2. Expression and acceptance of Heterogeneity.</p>	<p>3. Ethnic utilization of Cultural Mosaic.</p>	<p>4. Celebration regarding Cultural Diversity.</p>	<p>5. Viability of CRT.</p>
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Involvement of Parents and Students

Parent involvement as focused on by the Pakistani government through different activities towards getting educational goals is provided to be an important pillar of education. Diverse people from diverse cultures and backgrounds bring different experiences into the four walls of educational institutions. All teachers and students take benefit from these experiences. Teachers can integrate different activities with the help of parents' involvement in which students can perform different activities and parents can see their children growing and learning. The principal used to call the CMC meeting twice in the session. In our college students have the poor background and socio-economic stages. Most parents lack interest in their child's education. Parents are not well qualified. Despite these challenges, we tried our best to be meaningful and productive in teaching. Group formation, meeting with parents, classroom arrangement, and evaluation. He calls CMC twice a year to discuss students' problems with them. Student data preparation, group formation, meeting with parents, classroom arrangement and evaluation. Held CMC meetings thrice in an academic session that helped in getting parents involved in educational activities. The head is always ready to involve parents in the

affairs of students whenever the situation arises. On different occasions, parents are called to give their input to enhance the capability of the institute towards the accomplishment of identified goals.

Cultural days and especially cultural diversity day's celebrations

Due to our tough schedule, we cannot celebrate cultural days in the class. Usually, cultural days are not celebrated in the true sense, rather cultural festivals or provincial representations are an integral part of national days whenever they are celebrated e.g., 14 th August (Independence day), 23rd March (Pakistan day), 6th September (Defense day) etc. these celebrations bring people closer to one another eliminating regional boundaries. Different days Can be celebrated culturally this would add additional information on how different cultures celebrate this day. Once a year we celebrate or when FDE ask for it to do so. Cultural days are celebrated with great emotions. The cultural days are celebrated in the early morning at assembly sessions where students perform different activities like Duaa, the national anthem, and Pakistan Independence Day. Such events are not always celebrated in classrooms and even do not encourage such activities in the classroom. Eid days i.e. Eid ul Azha, Eid ul Fitar, Eid Milad ul Nabavi, Christmas, Basant etc. are

celebrated. Enthusiasm is shown on cultural days by students, staff and the head. With great zeal and forever cultural days are celebrated in our institution. We celebrate cultural days with great intent.

Efforts in the Creation of a Culturally Responsive Atmosphere

Principals, Staff and students cooperate and create a healthy environment. They share their cultural norms and also encourage them. Head, Staff and students work together displaying cultural competence, and skills in multicultural settings performing different and numerous activities. Students are encouraged to relate their instructional content to their cultural background for a better understanding of the diverse cultural norms of the community. Different Cultural Days are celebrated in the form of the 14th of August, and the 6th of September. The students from all the provinces can show their culture through tales, dramas and skits. We should formulate clear expectations for the students. We provide self-study material to the students, provide opportunities for revision of lectures and identify their social behavior. We explain it orally. We respect each child, whatever culture he has. They take the least interest in such activities and such an atmosphere is not found in the classroom. Head facilitates, students, make a poster, wear cultural dresses, and quiz programs are held. All efforts are directed towards the creation of a conducive atmosphere for use of CRT learning. Whenever cultural days are celebrated, the head and students participate gladly. All students' staff and

heads especially take a keen interest in the affairs of students' tasks on the occasion of cultural days.

Conclusion

Multiculturalism in the Context of Cultural Mosaic exists from some teachers' points of view. Diversity among Students regarding Cultures is part and parcel of our institutions and they have to be managed appropriately. Some of the teachers haven't idea about these two terms. Responses show that the Majority know about the terms Cultural Mosaic and Melting Pot, from a different perspective. Teachers have said that we have to respect and accept one another to deal with mosaic classrooms. As a teacher, it is our responsibility to shape the Character and thinking process of our students through Cultural Diversity. Data shows that Cultural Diversity seems prominent only on special occasions rather than felt deeply and managed properly. Teachers have the opinion that Cultural Diversity exists in their students up to some extent as students from other provinces are there in the classroom.

According to the In-Service teachers Prejudices, Superiority Complex, Harassment, and Non-Acceptance Attitude of Other Cultures, CRT is Unknown Terminology, and Language Barriers were existed for Collaborative Learning. They opined that diversity in Students exists in a considerable Proportion. Although teachers have pointed out a lot of challenges those can be overcome easily if they have a strong will. Teachers have not only pointed out challenges, but they were of the opinion that these challenges can be overcome by Sharing of Views, History Narration of Cultures,

Indigenous Gifts Sharing among Students, Different Activities of interaction among Students, Use Multiple Approaches to Teaching, Teachers Should Learn Diverse Languages, Teach according to Divers Learning Styles of Students, Safe Learning Environment, Use of Cultural Contextual Examples in Teaching, Group Learning, Caring Attitude, Friendly Atmosphere in Classroom, Mutual Respect, and Equal Opportunities in Expression.

As discussed above challenges may be overcome if the above strategies are adopted by the teachers tactfully and for this purpose students' prior knowledge has immense importance. So, Exploration of Student's Prior Knowledge, Experiences, and Expertise can be obtained through Discussion and Debates, Projects, Inquiry-Based Learning, Friendly Environment, Collaborative Learning, Brain Storming, and Use of Native Language Sparingly.

Recommendation

As a teacher of cultural mosaic classrooms and to ensure enhancement in students' performance, through culturally responsive teaching, we may

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build on the potential those are already brought by students in the class. We may respect the culture, norms, and value systems of other students. Mutual understandings, collaborative learning, high expectations from learners, and Parents may be involved through CMC and PTM in the learning process of their children. Teachers may be encouraged by the heads of the institution to learn about students' cultures that have representation in the classroom as well as other cultures that haven't representation in the classroom. Knowledge of learners' contexts may be got from books and the internet. Such type of facility may be easily available to them in institutions' Libraries, Computer Labs through Multi-Media or may be provided by the administration in a type of downloaded videos for watching at home. All such type of activities and provisions of facilities may be provided to the staff and students for their grooming to tackle the Cultural Mosaic classrooms' students in a way that promote and enhance the performance of students.

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